

Insights into Knowledge Reuse in ML Prototyping

Selin Coban*, Patrick Chrestin* and Horst Lichter*

*Research Group Software Construction, RWTH Aachen University

This manuscript was compiled on January 9, 2026

1. INTRODUCTION

Prototyping is central to ML development, where developers rapidly experiment with data, models, and algorithms to assess feasibility before building full systems. In this exploratory work, practitioners frequently reuse existing ideas, artifacts, and solutions. However, most prior research on reuse in ML has focused mainly on source code, overlooking broader forms of knowledge that guide prototyping.

This lack of insight risks valuable knowledge remaining fragmented or lost across projects. To address this gap, we conducted an interview study to examine how ML practitioners search for, evaluate, reuse, and retain knowledge during prototyping. We will investigate the following research questions:

RQ1: How do ML practitioners decide whether to reuse knowledge?

RQ2: How do ML practitioners retain relevant knowledge?

RQ3: How does the reuse process look like?

2. TERMINOLOGY

In the course of this summary, we will use the following terms, derived from existing concepts in knowledge management [1]:

- **Knowledge Element:** We use the term *knowledge element* to refer to explicit, codified units of knowledge that can be stored, communicated, and reused. Knowledge elements can have different *knowledge types*, e.g. terminology or solution design pattern.
- **Knowledge Source:** The artifact containing knowledge elements, such as a scientific paper or a StackOverflow post.

3. STUDY METHOD

Participants were given a simple ML classification problem to reduce the cognitive load and focus less on problem solving performance and more on decision-making and reuse strategies:

Prototyping Task: You are given the map of a public building. The map contains rooms, hallways, the library, the dining room, as well as all further offices. You are also given an extensive dataset of walking patterns, that are classified in GROUP-1, GROUP-2, GROUP-3, and OTHER. Your task now is to train a model that predicts the type of group when given a walking pattern.

This served as a basis for formulating interview questions that dive deeper into the reuse process and retention strategies.

Data Analysis

We analyzed the interview transcripts using Thematic Analysis (TA) following Braun and Clarke [2]. In addition to developing themes qualitatively, we counted their occurrences across transcripts, which provided complementary quantitative insights. This allowed us to examine not only what knowledge and practices participants reported, but also how frequently they appeared across the sample.

This document class was prepared on Overleaf and compiled with pdfL^AT_EX. No errors were found during the compilation process. Tau-class supports external editors, though additional setup may be required.

Participants

We conducted interviews with 18 participants from both academic and industry settings. Table 1 summarizes their demographic characteristics. Participants were recruited through professional networks, with the aim of achieving diversity in disciplinary backgrounds and expertise in software engineering and machine learning.

Table 1. Overview of Interview Participants by Position Type and Domain.

ID	Role	Domain	ML Exp. (yrs)	Org. Size
<i>Industry Practitioners</i>				
1	Software Dev.	IT Consulting & Software Dev.	3	<250
2 ^A	ML Practitioner	Public Transport	4.5	<50
3 ^A	ML Practitioner	Public Transport	9	<50
4	Student Worker	Information Processing	2	<50
5	Data Analyst	Finance	1	1
8	Data Owner	Clothing Retail	3	>10k
10	Software Dev.	Real Estate	2	<250
12	Consultant	Corporate Consulting	4	<50
14	Software Dev.	Process Automation	3	<50
15	Software Dev.	AI Consulting	4.5	<50
16	AI Expert	Optimization Software	1	<5k
18	Consultant	Green Energy	1.5	<5k
<i>Academic Practitioners</i>				
6	Ph.D. Student	Manufacturing	3	<10
7	Student	Computer Science	2	N/A
9	Ph.D. Student	Materials Engineering	5	<100
11	Ph.D. Student	Medicine	0.5	<25
13	Researcher	Mechanical Engineering	1	N/A
17 [†]	Ph.D. Student	Computer Vision	6	<25

[†] Interview split into two parts due to interviewee availability. IDs assigned in interview order; letters indicate participants from the same organization. N/A indicates students without formal organization size or unavailable information.

The interviews were conducted by one researcher using video conferencing tools between December 2024 and March 2025. All participants were informed about the purpose of the interview and the procedures for handling data. Each interview lasted between 32 and 87 minutes. All interviews were audio-recorded with participant consent, transcribed verbatim, pseudonymized, and stored for analysis.

Themes, codes, quotes, and their mappings are provided as supplementary material on Zenodo [3].

4. RESULTS

In the following we summarize the key results for each research question.

4.1. How do ML practitioners decide whether they want to reuse knowledge (RQ1)?

To investigate how participants evaluate knowledge for reuse, we coded the various criteria they described and grouped them into broader categories. This analysis revealed three recurring evaluation approaches:

- **Quality-based Evaluation:** In total, we identified 12 criteria, belonging to the key qualities *usability*, *credibility*, and *relevance*.

Figure 1. Concept Model of Reuse in ML Solution Prototyping

Figure 2. Knowledge Reuse Process in ML Solution Prototyping

- *Intuition-based Evaluation:* ML practitioners often draw on their intuition to rapidly evaluate the value of a knowledge element or the credibility of a knowledge source.
- *Experiment-based Evaluation:* For code artifacts, ML practitioners tend to evaluate their strengths, limitations, and overall suitability through direct experimentation.

4.2. How do ML practitioners retain relevant knowledge (RQ2)?

ML practitioners use various methods to document and manage relevant knowledge during problem-solving. To derive themes, we categorized codes based on the nature of the retention strategies:

- *Absent:* Participants relied on their memory, keeping knowledge elements 'in mind' (n = 10).
- *Ad-hoc Bookmarking:* Participants rely on the search history (n=2) or keep browser tabs open (n=7), often resulting in "tab chaos".
- *Unstructured Note-Taking:* Participants take physical or digital notes (n=8). Participants also annotated the code to document the origin or rationale of reused code snippets (n=3).
- *Structured Documentation Tools:* Participants use dedicated tools, such as Overleaf, Citavi or Microsoft Office products with filtering and tagging capabilities (n=X).

These strategies reflect whether knowledge is being retained solely for the duration of the current prototyping session or with the intention of supporting future reuse.

4.3. How does the knowledge reuse process look like? (RQ3)

Based on the study's findings, the key concepts and their relationships are summarized in the conceptual model shown in Figure 1.

Depending on the selected *search approach*, the *knowledge search* is performed using dedicated *search and retrieval tools*. These tools retrieve *knowledge sources* that capture *knowledge elements* of different *knowledge types*. The retrieved knowledge elements are then systematically assessed using a selected *evaluation approach* to determine their suitability for the current ML prototyping context. Accepted knowledge elements may subsequently be retained following a *retention approach*, thereby facilitating their future reuse within subsequent projects or iterations.

With these concepts, we can create a reuse process model, as depicted in Figure 2. This model illustrates the activities associated with knowledge reuse during the prototyping of ML solutions.

The process begins with the *search for knowledge* activity, in which *candidate knowledge* sources and elements relevant to the current ML problem context are identified. The *evaluate knowledge* activity assesses the candidate knowledge for its suitability of for reuse. Insights gained during evaluation may lead to a refinement of the search

approach, such as adopting more precise terminology for subsequent queries. If the candidate knowledge is deemed suitable for reuse, this accepted knowledge is incorporated into the ML prototype during *reuse knowledge* and captured in *retain knowledge* for future reference. *Retained knowledge* thus becomes accessible for both current and subsequent ML problems. If the candidate knowledge is found unsuitable, searching for knowledge is resumed. This cycle is repeated: after each round of reuse and retention, the search continues if the ML problem still remains unsolved. Otherwise, the process terminates once an adequate solution has been achieved.

5. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS ON TOOL SUPPORT

The evaluation of our interview study, presented in the previous section, clearly shows that there are still several areas for improvement to make ML solution prototyping more efficient. Below, we discuss some implications for supporting the prototyping of ML solutions using specialized tools.

The following observations characterize the current status of the central activities in the knowledge reuse process.

- *Search for knowledge:* ML practitioners utilize a variety of tools for searching and retrieving information, such as web search engines, scholarly literature databases, LLMs and combinations with other AI assistance tools.
- *Evaluate knowledge:* Three main evaluation approaches could be identified: quality-based, experiment-based, and intuition-driven. For quality-based evaluation in particular, we identified 12 criteria covering usability, credibility, and relevance of knowledge elements. Currently, there is no tool support for semi-automated evaluation or management of these criteria. Experiment-based evaluations are carried out in integrated development environments (IDEs).
- *Retain knowledge:* More than half of participants do not employ sustainable methods for retaining reusable knowledge. Knowledge thus tends to become siloed at the individual level, either mentally or within personal code archives, which is reflected by 17 participants who reported relying on human sources.

The results of our study point to several key directions for future tool development aimed at addressing the challenges of knowledge retention in ML prototyping. The lack of systematic approaches for retaining reusable knowledge arises not only from insufficient tooling but also from limited integration with practitioners' daily workflows and collaborative platforms.

6. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Internal Validity: All transcripts were independently coded by two researchers, with discrepancies resolved through discussion to reduce individual bias. Nevertheless, some subjectivity is inherent in

thematic analysis, and our findings are influenced by the aspects participants chose to share during their reflections.

External Validity: Our study involved interviews with 18 ML practitioners from both industry and academia, spanning diverse domains and roles. The relatively small sample size limits generalizability. Future research with larger samples could further strengthen the transferability of these findings.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Because opportunistic behavior discourages ML practitioners from investing time in manual knowledge retention, we want to investigate how retention processes can be supported or automated to promote knowledge reuse. To this end, we aim to develop a knowledge management tool that helps ML practitioners organize knowledge elements and sources by project and track their contributions to specific parts of an ML prototype. Furthermore, we aim to evaluate the validity of our knowledge reuse process, assessing the extent to which it reflects and accurately represents real-world practices.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Paul, M. Engelhart, I. Rus, and S. Sinha, “Knowledge Management in Software Engineering - A State-of-the-Art report”, Jan. 2001.
- [2] V. Braun and V. Clarke, “Successful Qualitative Research: A Practical Guide for Beginners”, 2013.
- [3] S. Coban and P. Chrestin, *Artifacts of the Paper “Knowledge Reuse in ML Solution Prototyping: Insights from an Interview Study”*, Zenodo, Jan. 2026. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18196720](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18196720). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18196720>.